

AGRESSION AMONG YOUTH- CAUSES AND RISK

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Abstract:

Aggressive behavior is a product of multiple factors operating on many levels in the absence of protective factor which affects youth largely within the context of their environment and experiences. A number of factors such as family environment, attitude towards religious sect, educational attitude, and dissatisfaction with job and media violence are influential in causing aggressive behavior among youth but relationships with peer group is such an important factor that is more significant in causing aggressive behavior among Aggression youth. Aggression has been defined (Loeber & Hay, 1997) as 'a category of behavior that causes or threatens physical harm to others' (p.373). The authors note that 'aggression' as generally used is not a unitary term but encompasses a variety of behaviors, including verbal aggression, bullying, physical fighting, robbery, rape and homicide .Youth indulgence themselves in various aggressive behaviors leading to significant psychosocial dysfunctions. The present study assesses the prevalence of aggression among youth and to assess the risk factors of aggression among youth

Keywords: Aggressive Behavior, Aggression, risk factors, youth

INTRODUCTION

Society has seen an increase in the incidents of aggression/violence among youth. It includes behaviors such as slapping, hitting, rape, recklessness, driving and shooting in school, truancy, road rage and other high-risk behaviors. Nearly 18.6% of females aged 12-17 got into a serious fight at school or work. 14.1% participated in a group-against-group fight and 5.7% attacked another person with an intent to seriously harm him/her In India, researchers have focused on factors such as perceived popularity among the peer group, romantic relations, the risk factors such as family system, environment, aggressive parents and academic performance, peer aggression, victimization and social relationships, Prevalence and Gender difference. The increasing crime rates and violent activities of youth in India have made the researchers to focus on aggression among youth. There is a need for the proper assessment of youth for aggression and development of prevention and intervention modules for youth in Indian context. The present study aims to understand the factors (prevalence, risk factors and protective factors associated with aggression .Aggression is defined as hostile, injurious, and destructive behavior. It is not an emotion, a motive, an attitude, or a diagnosis rather aggression is a behavioral response to an internal state. It is strongly suspected that aggression is due to both genetic (biological) factors and social (learned) factors. Human biology operates in a social context: the environment influences the development of nerve connections just as biological processes affect response to the environment (Mayer, 1997). The terms "aggression" and "aggressive behavior" are used interchangeably. Aggressive forms of behavior can be characterized by verbal or physical attack. Acts of aggression change during a person's life span. When young children lack verbal skills, aggression is predominantly physical. When verbal skills develop, they could be used as peaceful communication, but also for aggressive purposes. Aggression, like all types of behavior, involves biological forces. However, biological factors alone do not determine the development of aggression. The social environment of the individual is a powerful regulator of neurobiological processes and behavior. In other words, aggressive behavior is the outcome of the regulation of external and internal stimuli by living beings.

Characteristics

Aggressive behaviors can vary from problems with emotional regulation to severe and manipulative behaviors. There are various characteristics of aggression, which can include behaviors such as starting rumors; excluding others; arguing; bullying, both verbally (name-calling) and physically (pushing); threatening; striking back in anger; use of strong-arm tactics (to get something they want); and engaging in physical fights. Notably, aggressive behaviors do not always involve physical contact with another person. Verbal aggression in elementary school years, such as starting rumors, excluding others, and arguing, can be part of a developmental trajectory leading to adolescent delinquency and Conduct Disorder

Risk factors associated with aggression

1. substance abuse and aggression
2. Mood disturbance
3. Psychological problems
4. Frequency and correlation of academic experience and anger expression in college
5. Peer group violence
6. Anger management ways by peer group

OBJECTIVE

1. To determine the magnitude and types of aggressive behavior in youth.
2. To identify the influence of age and sex on aggressive behavior.
3. To find out the socio-economic characteristics.
4. To explore all possible factors affecting the aggressive behavior among youth.
5. To see the ways used by youth to express their aggression most of the time.
6. To check the attitude of family members towards youth aggression.
7. To analyze the factors that can lower down the aggression among youth.
8. To suggest measures to overcome aggression

RESULTS

Nearly, 17.7% of them experience of anger and 17% of them had physical aggression. The youth in the age group of 16-19 years had frequent experience of aggression in comparison to the age group of 20-26 years. There was a significant difference between males and females in the experience and expression of aggression. Females experienced less aggression in comparison to males. The work pressure (28.3%), alcohol (15.1%), violent activities (14.8%), exposure to family violence/violence in media (9.2%) had been associated with experience/expression of aggression/road rage. 34.8% reported indulgence in fights when they were angry. About 20.4% involved themselves in physical violence, 12.3% also used weapons during expression of aggression. Nearly 13.8% had experienced injuries due to fights. In the family context, 37% of the participants got hurts from their parents physically or emotionally, 14.8% of the parents had hurts each other emotionally or physically, 36.6% reported their parents had used physical means to discipline them. The mean score on the total of Buss-Perry Aggression Scale is 80.24, standard deviation is 19.59 F value is 63.71 and P value 0.00 (significance level 0.001) indicates significant difference among the mean scores of the group. The mean score of Indore (91.67) and Jammu (83.08) showed a high score on the total of Buss-Perry Aggression Scale, which indicates that Jammu and Indore groups have high-level of aggression compared with other regions. For management of aggression, the following themes emerged includes discussing with others (29%), solving problems individually (24.9%) and exploring the reasons for anger (18.1%); 37.1% perceives managing the anger with proper guidelines; 32.8% perceived explaining positives and negative effects of anger expression by encouraging healthy expression of anger; 23.9% perceives strict implementation of law such rules and regulation was the role of law and order in managing the anger in the society; 47.7% perceived encouraging healthy and positive programs in the media; 22.7% perceives promoting healthy expression of anger

and positive role models and 20.7% perceives promoting the information about counseling and its centers was the role of media in managing anger in the society. About 17.7% of the youth has high mean aggression score on Buss-Perry Aggression Scale. Males have high mean score on aggression than females. Males experienced more verbal aggression, physical aggression and anger than females. Younger age group (16-19 years) experienced more aggression than older age group (20-26 years). The risk factors of the youth aggressions were identified as physical abuse in childhood, substance abuse such as alcohol and tobacco, negative peer influence, family violence, academic disturbance, psychological problems attention deficit-hyperactivity disorder, suspicious, loneliness, mood disturbance, negative childhood experience and TV and media.

Youth Violence: National Statistics

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The present work highlighted the presence of aggression among youth. Its association with reported that work pressure, substance use, violent activities, family disturbance, road rage, mood disturbance, psychological problems and peer relationships. Resilience had a negative relationship with substance use, mood disturbance, physical abuse, sexual abuse, Failure in academics, missed college regularly, anger expressed in school or college, childhood experience, ADHD, Family influence, peer influence, media influence and psychological problems. It management has been highlighted in the form of discussing with others, solving problems individually, exploring the reasons for anger; educating themselves about the positives and negative effects of anger expression by encouraging healthy expression of anger; strict implementation of Law such rules and regulation in managing the anger in the society; healthy and positive programs in the media and healthy expression of aggression; sensitization about the availability of counseling and its management. Gender difference exits for management of aggression. It was corroborated by other studies. Younger age group had high expression of aggression. Males were more likely to be aggressors or victims than females Boys were found to be more physically and verbally aggressive than girls, but girls used more indirect aggression at the higher year levels Higher percentage of women engaged in verbal aggression (95.3% vs. 92.8%), whereas the males engaged in more severe physical aggression (4.6% vs. 2.0%) and produced worse consequences for their female partners' health (especially slight cuts/slight bruises, broken nose, black eye, broken bone and requiring medical treatment/hospitalization). Women reportedly attacked their partners while under the influence of emotional states of intense anger (22.4% vs. 13.9%), whereas males did so in response to aggression received (13.0% vs. 6.6%). Physical aggression decreased significantly across the age groups, but health consequences became more severe with age (e.g., broken nose, black eye, broken bone, went from 1% at 16 years to

4.5% at 20 years of age Risk factors strongly related to later violence were distributed among the five domains of hyperactivity (parent rating), low academic performance, peer delinquency and availability of drugs in the neighborhood predicted violence from ages 10, 14 and 16 years. Youths exposed to multiple risks were notably more likely than others to engage in later violence A dependent group had high mean scores for state anger, trait anger and expression/experience of anger. They had lower anger control and quality-of-life. Alcohol dependent persons have high expression and experience of anger leading to low quality-of-life A history of abuse, failing a grade and dealing drugs was also independently associated with violence while having a regular partner was protective Delinquent peer influences, antisocial personality traits, depression and parents/guardians who used psychological abuse in intimate relationships were consistent risk factors for youth violence and aggression. Poor academic performance, peer rejection and psychosomatic complaints with high-levels of anger. It has implications in the form of screening of risk factors/vulnerabilities for emotional dyscontrol among youth, teachers should pay attention to aggression related behavior (verbal/non-verbal) and help children/youth to handle them in a better way and psycho education for the parents; Need for interaction of academic institute, policy makers and parents: Reducing academics distress, ability to handle pressure or frustration or failure; development of intervention module for management of aggression. Aggression that begins in the earliest years of life is clearly linked to delinquent and criminal behavior in later life. Preventative interventions during the early years of life for at risk families reduce the prevalence and the seriousness of such behavior problems. When the costs of failing to provide supportive contexts for developmental health, as measured by increased antisocial behavior, are examined, it is clear that they are substantial. Conversely, future savings from early interventions that prevent these problems are substantial.

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